

***IN-SITU* SYNTHESIS OF POLYAMIDE COMPOSITES WITH RECYCLE CARBON FIBER**

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ABSTRACT

Here in, rCF and polyamide 66 (PA66) were prepared by *in-situ* polymerization. As a result, rCF was highly dispersed in PA66. Due to the low interfacial area as well as the poor interfacial interaction, the thermal decomposition temperature decreased by the addition of a small amount of rCF. On the other hand, at high content region, the excellent reinforcement effects of rCF were exploited. The composites with high content of rCF also exhibited significant improvement in the mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, polymer composite materials are expected to replace metal materials due to their light weight and ease of processing. In particular, carbon fiber-reinforced plastics are attracting attention as materials for automobiles and aircraft because of their light weight, high strength, and heat resistance. However, the high cost of manufacturing carbon fiber (CF) and the environmental impact of the manufacturing process have slowed the spread of CF despite its demand. One countermeasure is to recycle CF. Although recycled carbon fiber (rCF) has the problem of uneven quality due to the fact that it is a recycled material, it is attracting attention as a solution to environmental problems such as global warming, which has become an issue in recent years.

In this study, composite materials of rCF and polyamide 66 (PA66) were prepared by *in-situ* polymerization. In *in-situ* polymerization, the filler is added to the solvent used to synthesize the polymer, and the polymer is synthesized in the presence of the filler. Since the synthesis proceeds while the filler remains dispersed in the solvent, the dispersibility of the polymer composite can be improved.

PA66, which was selected as the base material this time, is in demand in a wide range of fields such as automobile parts and electrical and electronic equipment because of its high strength, heat resistance, and chemical resistance among polymeric materials. Therefore, it is a substance that is being researched for further improvement of its mechanical and thermal properties.

2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

Hexamethylenediamine was added to rCF water dispersion, and then sodium hydroxide was added. The mixture was stirred for one hour to obtain solution A. Solution A was added to a mixture of carbon tetrachloride and adipoyl chloride and polymerized at the interface. The resultant was then purified by reprecipitation, dried and melt-pressed to obtain PA66/rCF composites with a thickness of 0.2 mm. The filler content was 0 to 30 wt%.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Optical image

Figure 1: Optical image of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites.

Figure 1 shows optical images of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites. The transparency of the composites decreased with increasing of the filler content. The composites with more than 5.0 wt% of rCF is almost opaque. From these images of the composites, the agglomerates of rCF were not observed.

3.2 SEM

Figure 2: SEM images of rCF and fracture surfaces of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites.

Figure 2 shows SEM images of rCF and fracture surfaces of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites. In the

PA66/rCF composite aggregate of rCF was no observed, showing that rCF was highly dispersed in the composite. In the composites, a number of holes can be seen where the rCF has been pulled out. This indicates that the interaction between PA66 and rCF is weak.

3.3 XRD

Figure 3: X-ray diffraction profiles of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites.

Figure 3 shows the X-ray diffraction profiles of rCF, PA66 and PA66/rCF composites. In the profile of rCF, (002) was appeared at around 2θ of 25° . Peaks corresponding to (100) and (010) of PA66 were observed at approximately 2θ of 21° and 25° , respectively. These peaks were also observed at the same 2θ in the profiles of the PA66/rCF composites, suggesting that crystalline structure of PA66 was maintained even after the addition of rCF. In addition, since the (010) of PA66 overlaps with the (002) derived from rCF, the intensity of the peak at 2θ of 25° increases with increasing rCF content.

3.4 Thermal Properties

Figure 4: DSC thermogram of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites.

Figure 4 shows DSC thermogram of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites. The endothermic peak appeared at around 263 °C corresponds to the melting point, while the exothermic appeared at around peak near 230 °C corresponds to the crystallization temperature. Both the melting point and the crystallization temperature were not affected by the addition of rCF even at high content. These results indicate that the crystalline structure of PA66 is maintained despite the increased rCF content.

Figure 5: Thermogravimetric traces of rCF, PA66 and PA66/rCF composites.

Figure 5 shows thermogravimetric traces of rCF, PA66 and PA66/rCF composites. The 5% weight loss was defined as thermal decomposition temperature. At the filler content up to 10 wt%. The thermal decomposition temperature largely decreased. It was suggested that rCF inhibited the polymerization of PA66. Therefore, the decrease in the thermal decomposition temperature of the polymer matrix resulted in the lower thermal decomposition temperature of the composites. In the process of in-situ polymerization, resulting in a lower molecular weight.

On the other hand, the thermal decomposition temperature increased at the high filler content more than 20 wt%. For example, the thermal decomposition temperature increased about 20°C by the addition of 30 wt% of rCF. It was assumed that the molecular weight of PA66 in these composites with high filler content also decreased. However, the excellent reinforcement effect of rCF, derived from its rigid structure was dominant for these composites, resulted in the high thermal resistance.

3.5 Mechanical Properties

Figure 6: Stress-strain curves of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites.

Figure 6 shows stress-strain curves of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites. The Young's modulus which corresponds to initial gradient, significantly increased by the addition of rCF. In addition, the tensile strength, the maximum stress, increased for the composites with high content.

Figure 7: Young's modulus and tensile strength of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites.

Figure 7 on the left shows the Young's modulus and the figure on the right shows the Tensile strength of PA66 and PA66/rCF composites. The Young's modulus increased with increasing of rCF content. Especially in the region of high filler content, the composites showed high Young's modulus. For example, compared to PA66, the Young's modulus increased by 3.6 times by the addition of 30 wt% of rCF. On the other hand, the tensile strength decreased, for the composites with low filler content. As mentioned before, the molecular weight could be decreased by the addition of rCF, due to the process of in-situ polymerization, resulted in decrease in the mechanical properties of the polymer matrix. However, the tensile strength increased for the composites with high filler content. It increased by 1.8 times by the addition of 30 wt% of rCF, showing the excellent reinforcement effect of rCF.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the PA66 composites, rCF was highly dispersed by in-situ polymerization. The thermal decomposition temperature was significantly reduced by adding small amounts of rCF, but increased at 20 wt% of rCF. The Young's modulus and the tensile strength increased by the addition of rCF. A significant increase in the Young's modulus was observed at more than 10 wt%.